

UNIVERSITAT_{DE}
BARCELONA

UB CoARA Action Plan 2024-2027

University of Barcelona Action Plan to reform
the evaluation of research activity

Version 3.0

Approved by the UB CoARA Steering Committee on 30 June
2025

Preamble

The University of Barcelona intends to pursue the commitments of the CoARA Agreement for the reform of university research evaluation, which will require the implementation of a series of specific processes. The design, implementation and execution mechanisms of these processes involve the entire community, as they correspond to calls and initiatives led by the institution.

The medium-term goal is to progressively promote the integration of a new culture and new evaluation criteria for the research activity of UB teaching and research staff in the different stages of their careers, applying these changes in line with the recommendations established in the international CoARA Agreement. These changes will be introduced gradually, across the whole of the university community, assimilating any emerging developments providing scope for improvement.

As the **driving team** behind the implementation of the CoARA commitments, in January 2023 the UB set up the **UB CoARA Work Group**, formed by the vice-rectors responsible for research (VREC), doctoral studies (VDOC) and teaching and research staff (VPDI), and the delegates of the Rector responsible for open science and internal research promotion, with the support of a management specialist. In July 2024, the UB CoARA Work Group incorporated two new members: the Vice-Rector for Quality Policy (VPQU) and a second management specialist, who will coordinate the strands of the Action Plan. On 29 October 2024, the UB CoARA Work Group agreed to update its lines of action, schedule and initiatives in the UB CoARA Action Plan and monitor it on an annual basis as a continuous improvement measure. Since June 2025, the UB CoARA Work Group is renamed **UB CoARA Steering Committee**.

An [annual monitoring report](#), which includes the progress status of actions already initiated, is prepared as a result of the annual monitoring of the Action Plan. The monitoring report is the basis for generating a revised version of the Action Plan, if applicable.

The UB CoARA Steering Committee will ensure that the implementation of the UB CoARA Action Plan is aligned with the institutional human resources strategy for research ([HR Excellence in Research UB](#)).

As a signatory to the CoARA Agreement, the UB assumes the four core commitments and must therefore strive to ensure that its selection processes and research initiatives:

- Acknowledge the diversity of research activities and careers in the framework of different research settings and requirements.
- Base research evaluation primarily on qualitative strategies, in which peer review plays a key role, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators.
- Remove from research evaluation strategies the inappropriate use of journal- and publication-based metrics; in particular, inappropriate use of the journal impact factor (JIF) and the *h*-index.
- Avoid the use of rankings of research organizations in the evaluation of research activity.

The UB CoARA Action Plan sets out the institutional commitments to support the Agreement, which include commitments concerning the development of new criteria, tools and processes for research evaluation, and to promote mutual learning, guarantee the provision of information about the process, and ensure that new evaluation approaches are evidence-based.

ub.edu/web/coara

UB CoARA Action Plan 2024-2027 (version 3.0)

CoARA commitments	Codes for lines of action	Lines of action	Action codes	Actions	Start: 2024 Q1	End: 2027 Q4	Direction	Main participants	Codes for indicators	Evaluation mechanisms (indicators)
5. Commit resources for reforming research evaluation.	CoARA05-01-000	Ensure institutional commitment to CoARA principles.	CoARA05-01-001	Create the UB CoARA Work Group.	2024 Q1	2024 Q2	VPQU	VPDI, VDOC, DCOB, APIR, VREC	CoARA05-01-001-i1	Agreement to create the UB CoARA Work Group.
			CoARA05-01-002	Draft and approve the UB CoARA Action Plan.	2024 Q2	2024 Q3	VPQU	CD UB CoARA	CoARA05-01-002-i1	UB CoARA Action Plan.
			CoARA05-01-003	Monitor the UB CoARA Action Plan on an annual basis.	2024 Q3	2027 Q4	VPQU	CD UB CoARA	CoARA05-01-003-i1	Periodic action. Annual monitoring report on the UB CoARA Action Plan.
6. Review and develop criteria, tools and processes to evaluate research activity.	CoARA06-01-000	Align internal calls for applications in which research is evaluated with CoARA principles.	CoARA06-01-001	Prepare an institutional handbook on the evaluation of research activity using CoARA principles.	2024 Q4	2025 Q4	DCOB	VPDI, VREC, VDOC, APIR	CoARA06-01-001-i1	Publication of the <i>UB handbook on the evaluation of research activity based on CoARA principles</i> .
			CoARA06-01-002	Review and update the terms and conditions of the recruitment programme for predoctoral research staff in order to integrate CoARA principles into each phase in the process.	2025 Q2	2026 Q1	VDOC		CoARA06-01-002-i1	Terms and conditions of calls for applications updated with the progressive incorporation of CoARA criteria.
			CoARA06-01-003	Review and update the terms and conditions of the recruitment programme for predoctoral research staff under specific research funding agreements in order to integrate CoARA principles into each phase in the process.	2025 Q2	2026 Q1	VREC	VDOC, VPDI	CoARA06-01-003-i1	Terms and conditions of calls for applications updated with the progressive incorporation of CoARA criteria.
			CoARA06-01-004	Review and update the terms and conditions of the recruitment programme for temporary contract researchers (UB and Serra Hunter assistant professors) in order to incorporate CoARA principles into each phase of the selection process.	2026 Q1	2027 Q1	VPDI		CoARA06-01-004-i1	Terms and conditions of calls for applications updated with the progressive incorporation of CoARA criteria.

CoARA commitments	Codes for lines of action	Lines of action	Action codes	Actions	Start: 2024 Q1	End: 2027 Q4	Direction	Main participants	Codes for indicators	Evaluation mechanisms (indicators)
			CoARA06-01-005	Review and update the promotion of research chairs and the regulations of internal calls for applications for full professorships in order to integrate CoARA principles into each phase in the process.	2026 Q1	2027 Q1	VPDI	VREC	CoARA06-01-005-i1	Terms and conditions of calls for applications updated with the progressive incorporation of CoARA criteria.
			CoARA06-01-006	Review and update the terms and conditions of calls for applications for permanent teaching and research staff positions in order to integrate CoARA principles into each phase in the process.	2026 Q1	2027 Q1	VPDI		CoARA06-01-006-i1	Terms and conditions of calls for applications updated with the progressive incorporation of CoARA criteria.
			CoARA06-01-007	Distribute the <i>UB handbook on the evaluation of research activity based on CoARA principles</i> among members of the evaluation and selection committees.	2026 Q1	2026 Q1	VPDI		CoARA06-01-007-i1	Percentage of committees informed.
			CoARA06-01-008	Define mechanisms for the internal prioritization of candidates in the framework of external calls for applications (e.g., ICREA Sènior, Consolidació, ATRAE, or similar).	2026 Q1	2026 Q4	VREC	VPDI, VEIT	CoARA06-01-008-i1	Publication of prioritization criteria.
			CoARA06-01-009	Disseminate criteria among personnel responsible for prioritizing candidates.	2027 Q1	2027 Q2	VREC	VPDI, VEIT	CoARA06-01-009-i1	% of external calls for applications applying prioritization criteria.
7. Ensure that the university community is informed about the reform of research evaluation and offer transparency, communication, guidance and training on evaluation processes and criteria.	CoARA07-01-000	Train members of the UB community in the application of CoARA principles.	CoARA07-01-001	Create a CoARA portal within the institutional website.	2025 Q1	2025 Q2	VPQU	DWEB	CoARA07-01-001-i1	Creation of UB CoARA website.
			CoARA07-01-002	Organize events hosted by guest specialists on research evaluation based on international best practices and guidelines.	2025 Q2	2027 Q4	VREC	OTVREC, DCOB	CoARA07-01-002-i1	Periodic action. Satisfaction of attendees.
			CoARA07-01-003	Organize training activities on the CoARA principles for PTGAS	2024 Q2	2027 Q4	VREC	VGRT, DCOB, FPTGAS	CoARA07-01-003-i1	Periodic action. % participation (with respect to no. invited).

CoARA commitments	Codes for lines of action	Lines of action	Action codes	Actions	Start: 2024 Q1	End: 2027 Q4	Direction	Main participants	Codes for indicators	Evaluation mechanisms (indicators)
				involved in research management and evaluation.					CoARA07-01-003-i2	Satisfaction of attendees with training received.
			CoARA07-01-004	Organize training activities on CoARA principles for PDI.	2025 Q4	2027 Q4	VREC	IDP, DCOB, VDOC	CoARA07-01-004-i1	Periodic action. % participation (with respect to no. invited).
									CoARA07-01-004-i2	Satisfaction of attendees with training received.
			CoARA07-01-005	Prepare and publish internal information, guides and marketing campaigns on UB criteria for research evaluation.	2026 Q1	2027 Q4	DCOB	VREC, CD CoARA UB, CRAI, CI	CoARA07-01-005-i1	Publication of documents.
8. Exchange information on experiences and to facilitate mutual learning inside and outside the CoARA coalition.	CoARA08-01-000	Promote the exchange of information and best practices with members of CoARA.	CoARA08-01-001	Promote the UB's participation in the CoARA General Assembly, the National Chapter Spain and, periodically, in other specific work groups of strategic interest.	2024 Q2	2027 Q4	VPQU	CD CoARA UB	CoARA08-01-001-i1	Periodic action. Summary of participation in the annual monitoring report of the UB CoARA Action Plan.
9. Inform about advances in adhesion to the principles and implementation of commitments; evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the latest studies on research evaluation, using open data to gather evidence and generate new research.	CoARA09-01-000	Promote the use of a specific internal communication strategy on the implementation of actions foreseen in the UB CoARA Action Plan.	CoARA09-01-001	Publish on the UB CoARA website documentation, indicators and infographics detailing advances in the implementation of CoARA principles at the UB.	2024 Q3	2027 Q4	VPQU	CD CoARA UB	CoARA09-01-001-i1	Periodic action. Website update.
			CoARA09-01-002	Implement and review internal and external channels of communication on the UB's actions in the framework of CoARA.	2024 Q3	2024 Q4	VRPQ		CoARA09-01-002-i1	Creation of a corporate email account, coara@ub.edu .

CoARA commitments	Codes for lines of action	Lines of action	Action codes	Actions	Start: 2024 Q1	End: 2027 Q4	Direction	Main participants	Codes for indicators	Evaluation mechanisms (indicators)
10. Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the latest studies on research evaluation, using open data to gather evidence and generate new research.	CoARA10-01-000	Promote research into research evaluation at the UB.	CoARA10-01-001	Analyse the international state of the art on new evaluation metrics and models.	2025 Q1	2027 Q4	Àngel Borrego (PDI, FIMA)	VREC, VPDI	CoARA10-01-001-i1	Document on UB research groups that analyse research evaluation.
			CoARA10-01-002	Carry out simulations to assess the impact of the incorporation of new evaluation metrics and criteria into the academic commitment plan (PDA).	2025 Q1	2027 Q4	AAPPDI	VPDI	CoARA10-01-001-i2	UB PDA.

Structure of action codes: *CoARA0X-0Y-00Z(-iN)-X*: no. commitment / Y: no. line of action / Z: no. action / iN: indicator no. (coded for indicators only).

Acronyms

AAPPDI: Special Assistant for Analysis of the Teaching and Research Staff Body
 APIR: Special Assistant for Internal Promotion of Research
 CD CoARA UB: UB CoARA Steering Committee
 CI: Institutional Communication
 CRAI: Learning and Research Resources Centre
 DCOB: Delegate of the Rector for Scientific Journals and Open Science
 DWEB: Web Development
 FIMA: Faculty of Information and Audiovisual Media
 FPTGAS: Technical, Management, Administrative and Services Staff Training
 IDP: Institute for Professional Development
 OTVREC: Technical Office of the Vice-Rectorate for Research
 PDI: Teaching and Research Staff
 PI: Research Staff
 VDOC: Vice-Rector for Doctoral Studies, Trainee Research Staff, Talent Attraction and Dissemination
 VREC: Vice-Rector for Research
 VPDI: Vice-Rector assigned to the Rector and for Teaching and Research Staff
 VPQU: Vice-Rector for Quality Policy
 VEIT: Vice-Rector for Entrepreneurship, Innovation and Transfer
 VGRT: Deputy General Manager for Research, Transfer and Innovation

Codi accions	Accions	2024		2025			2026			2027			2028	
		T1	T2	T3	T4	T1	T2	T3	T4	T1	T2	T3	T4	T1
	Compromís 5													
CoARA05-01-001	Crear el Grup de Treball CoARA UB.													
CoARA05-01-002	Elaborar i aprovar el Pla d'acció CoARA UB.													
CoARA05-01-003	Fer el seguiment anual del Pla d'acció CoARA UB.													
	Informe anual 2024													
	Informe anual 2025													
	Informe anual 2026													
	Informe anual 2027													
	Compromís 6													
CoARA06-01-001	Elaborar una guia institucional per a l'avaluació de la recerca basada en els principis CoARA.													
CoARA06-01-002	Revisar i actualitzar les bases de les convocatòries del programa de contractació de personal investigador posdoctoral a càrrec de finançament específic de recerca per tal d'incorporar els principis CoARA en les diferents fases del procés.													
CoARA06-01-003	Revisar i actualitzar les bases de les convocatòries del programa de contractació de personal investigador posdoctoral a càrrec de finançament específic de recerca per tal d'incorporar els principis CoARA en les diferents fases del procés.													
CoARA06-01-004	Revisar i actualitzar les bases de les convocatòries del programa de contractació de professorat docent i docent investigador (lectors UB i lectors Serra Hùnter) per tal d'incorporar els principis CoARA en les diferents fases del procés.													
CoARA06-01-005	Revisar i actualitzar la promoció de càtedres d'excel·lència de recerca i les bases de les convocatòries dels concursos d'acció a places de docent de càtedres d'universitat (promoció interna) per tal d'incorporar els principis CoARA en les diferents fases del procés.													
CoARA06-01-006	Revisar i actualitzar les bases de les convocatòries dels concursos per a la contractació de personal docent investigador permanent per tal d'incorporar els principis CoARA en les diferents fases del procés.													
CoARA06-01-007	Difondre la Guia UB de recomanacions per a l'avaluació de la recerca basada en els principis CoARA entre els membres de les comissions d'avaluació i de selecció de places.													
CoARA06-01-008	Definir mecanismes de prioritització interna per proposar candidatures en el marc de convocatòries externes (p. ex. ICREA-Sènior, Consolidació, ATRAE, o similars).													
CoARA06-01-009	Difusió dels criteris entre les persones responsables de prioritzar candidatures.													
	Compromís 7													
CoARA07-01-001	Crear un lloc web CoARA dins el web institucional.													
CoARA07-01-002	Organitzar jornades a càrrec d'experts en avaluació de la recerca segons bones pràctiques i rellevants internacionals.													
	Fornació d'experts 2025													
	Fornació d'experts 2026													
	Fornació d'experts 2027													
CoARA07-01-003	Organitzar activitats formatives sobre els principis CoARA per al PTGAS relacionat amb la gestió i l'avaluació de la recerca.													
	Fornació a PTGAS 2024													
	Fornació a PTGAS 2025													
	Fornació a PTGAS 2026													
	Fornació a PTGAS 2027													
CoARA07-01-004	Organitzar activitats formatives sobre els principis CoARA per al PDI.													
	Fornació a PDI 2025													
	Fornació a PDI 2026													
	Fornació a PDI 2027													
CoARA07-01-005	Editar i publicar materials informatius, guies i campanyes de màrqueting intern sobre els criteris UB per a l'avaluació de la recerca.													
	Compromís 8													
CoARA08-01-001	Fomentar la participació de la UB en l'Assemblea General de la CoARA, en el National Chapter Spain i, eventualment, en altres grups de treball específics que siguin d'interès estratègic.													
	Informe de participació 2024													
	Informe de participació 2025													
	Informe de participació 2026													
	Informe de participació 2027													
	Compromís 9													
CoARA09-01-001	Publicar al lloc web CoARA UB documentació, indicadors i infografies per informar sobre els avenços en la implementació a la UB dels principis CoARA.													
	Informe de progrés 2024													
	Informe de progrés 2025													
	Informe de progrés 2026													
	Informe de progrés 2027													
CoARA09-01-002	Implementar i actualitzar els canals de comunicació interns i externs sobre les accions CoARA a la UB.													
	Compromís 10													
CoARA10-01-001	Analitzar l'estat de la qüestió internacional sobre noves mètriques i models d'avaluació													
	Informe d'avanços 2025													
	Informe d'avanços 2026													
	Informe d'avanços 2027													
CoARA10-01-002	Elaborar simulacions per avaluar l'impacte de la incorporació de noves mètriques i criteris d'avaluació en el pla de dedicació acadèmica (PDA).													